

Study Habits and Academic Performance of HUMSS 12 Students During Modular Learning Modality

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Germaine Mae Yray

Tuyom Senior High School, Schools Division of Carcar City, Cebu, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-3169-6146>

Jannah Jane Bueno

Tuyom Senior High School, Schools Division of Carcar City, Cebu, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7182-2944>

Ehricka Mae Alcantara

Tuyom Senior High School, Schools Division of Carcar City, Cebu, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0001-4427-886X>

Rexel Omilgo

Tuyom Senior High School, Schools Division of Carcar City, Cebu, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-8080-8471>

Shelby Mae Traverro

Tuyom Senior High School, Schools Division of Carcar City, Cebu, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0000-8544-9015>

Jeremy Onipa

Tuyom Senior High School, Schools Division of Carcar City, Cebu, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-7528-2702>

John Raeven Lapinid

Tuyom Senior High School, Schools Division of Carcar City, Cebu, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-6635-9419>

Clark Garces

Tuyom Senior High School, Schools Division of Carcar City, Cebu, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-3149-4499>

Dm Cabrerros

Tuyom Senior High School, Schools Division of Carcar City, Cebu, Philippines
<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-8023-629X>

Abstract

This research aimed to discover the correlation of study habits and academic performance of HUMSS 12 students during modular learning modality on SY. 2021-2022 where the respondents are in 10th grade. It employed a descriptive correlational research design. Survey questionnaires were utilized in gathering the necessary data for the study. The results of this study revealed no significant correlation between the respondents' study habits and academic performance in terms of Delay Avoidance. But it also revealed that there is a significant correlation between the students' academic performance and study habits in terms of Work Methods. Thus, the null hypothesis for Delay Avoidance is accepted and the null hypothesis for Work Methods is rejected. Based on the findings of the study, the researchers recommend for the students, teachers, parents, and the academe to improve and adjust learning and teaching styles for better acquisition of knowledge if they switch to modular set-up.

Keywords: *Study Habits, Academic Performance, Modular Learning, Humanities and Social Sciences, Tuyom Senior High School*

Introduction

The emergence of COVID-19 in the Philippines resulted in significant changes in the educational landscape. A major example is the introduction of a new method of teaching by the Department of Education. Most education systems have been forced to adopt alternatives to face-to-face teaching and learning as a result of the COVID-19 dilemma. As a result of school shutdown, many education systems have shifted their operations online and made them modular so that teaching can proceed accordingly (OECD, 2020). In the Philippine educational system, public schools led by the Department of Education (DepEd) implemented modular distance learning modality. This sudden shift of the mode of instruction does not only pose difficulties to the teachers but to the students as well (Castoverde & Acala, 2021).

Self-learning has been a struggle for students who were in a state of shock with the sudden shift of the country's education system. Developing effective study habits are important for productive and better learning, especially during the implementation of modular learning modality in schools. According to Tus et. al (2020), study habits can be defined as either effective or ineffective depending on how well it helps the students. The importance of study habits in the students' lives was highlighted by Arieta, Gementiza & Saco (2019). In their study, they

concluded that each student's success or failure is determined by the influence of the students' good study habits in doing their homework, active participation in class, managing their time, being focused, and working hard.

One of the most important metrics used to assess the quality of education in schools is students' academic achievement or performance. According to Tus (2020), academic performance is an important component of the constellation of elements that determine student success. It plays an important part in education, primarily as a tangible instrument for evaluating a student's learning process. Furthermore, students' academic performance has a vital role in developing high-quality graduates who will serve as excellent leaders and manpower for the country's economic and social development (Alos, Caranto, and David, 2019).

Academic success is a complicated process that is influenced by a variety of factors, including study habits (Jafari et al., 2019). According to Ebele (2019), the students cannot function and advance academically without developing study habits. In a study by Fouche (2019), the influence of the students' good study habits has shown a significant positive correlation on their academic performance. This implied that the students who acquired effective study habits were more likely to achieve academic success and have better academic performance in school. However, in contrast to the previous studies mentioned, in a study conducted by Tus (2020) entitled "The Influence of Study Attitudes and Study Habits on The Academic Performance Of The Students," the students' study attitudes and study habits revealed non-significance on their academic performance.

In an interview with the HUMSS students in Tuyom Senior High School, they stated that they had a hard time getting high scores during the modular learning modality as they don't have an effective study habit. They added that for them, it is important to develop study habits as it can have a strong connection to academic success. Thus, Rabia et al. (2017) calls for attention in studies about study habits and academic performance as it is assumed that it determines scholastic or academic success.

Considering the possible significance of study habits' influence to academic success and performance, the researchers sought to reveal its correlation during the implementation of modular modality learning. Through this study, the researchers aimed to contribute to education and the institution by discovering and assessing the correlation between the HUMSS 12 students' study habits and their academic performance during the modular set-up in the SY. 2021-2022 where the respondents are in 10th grade.

Literature Review

According to Hernando-Malipot (2020), the COVID-19 pandemic has become a global health issue and has had a major impact on education. He reported that of all the alternative learning modalities offered by the Department of Education (DepEd), most students prefer to use the modular distance learning options. According to Llego (2020), modular distance learning is learners' learning at their own pace, in their own way and using self-learning modules (SLMs). Moreover, Angkarini (2021) highlighted that the new mode of learning requires students to adjust their study habits and be different from what they receive in conventional face-to-face classes.

Additionally, Gonzalez (2017) states that studying is a skill. These skills of study must initially be acquired by the students, practiced and eventually established in order to become a high performing student. To take responsibility for the learning process, establish practical goals, become aware of performance and progress, use time sensibly, as well as comprehend and retain content, there are some habits for effective study.

Moreover, according to Losare Jr. (2019), study habits simply mean how a pupil manages his/ her time in such a way that he/she can review and study regularly. He also said that study habits are the ways that you study - the habits that you have formed during your school years. There are different kinds of study habits. Jato (2014) said that study habit as a repeated and regular activity which includes reading, note-taking or holding study groups done by students in order to succeed in learning.

Delay Avoidance

As reported by Gonzalez (2017), delay avoidance is a style of study wherein students do not procrastinate on tasks. It also refers to the student's capacity or ability to refrain from situations that may prevent him from studying his lessons at once. Llavore, Duran, and Dungan (2015) state that good study habits are essential for students of all ages, particularly when it comes to delay avoidance, which slows down work. These kinds of behaviors will also impact how well students do in their academic careers.

According to Derossis et al. (2016), they stated that there is a small but significant correlation between academic performance of students and delay avoidance. It indicates that students who put off completing their assignments, perform worse in class. With this, the researchers conclude that there is really a correlation between delay avoidance and academic performance of students. Moreover, Memiş & Kandemir (2019) reports that there is a strong, moderately positive, and significant relationship between study habit and delay avoidance.

Furthermore, when it comes to delay avoidance, students often take a while to get into studying. They find themselves feeling tired, bored, or sleepy when they finally sit down to hit the books. As a result, they end up wasting a lot of time chatting, watching TV, listening to the radio, going to the movies, and so on, instead of focusing on their studies (Tus, 2020).

However, Magno (2020) found that there is no significant correlation between study habits and delay avoidance saying that only the work methods are correlated with academic performance of students especially in learning areas like English and Mathematics.

Work Methods

According to Aquino (2016), work methods are indicators of productive study techniques. It also shows organization and system in studying lessons. Study habits have continuously been recognized to affect academic performance especially in terms of work methods. Excellence of good work method is the ability of doing things out of habit towards understanding knowledge and skills such as reading effectively, note taking, mastering time and balancing play and search (Gonzalez, 2017).

On the report of Magno (2020), work method shows how the students go about solving the problems using different ways of understanding information. Among other study habits, the work method was considered the most powerful predictor. This particular study habit appears helpful in instances where one has to master particular materials like when studying for tests.

Moreover, Aquino (2016) reported that students perform higher in work methods than the other study habits which stipulates that there is a visible significant correlation between students' academic performance and their study habits. It also showed that only work methods produced a correlation with the two. Derossis et al. (2016) states that among other study habits, work methods are the most powerful indicator of academic success.

Furthermore, Tus J. (2020) states that study habit indicator such as work methods have a strong correlation to students' academic performance that denotes their promptness in accomplishing academic requirements, freedom from wasteful delay and distraction, the use of effective study procedures, efficiency in doing academic assignments, and how-to-study skills.

Goud (2018) revealed that students have a positive attitude towards study habits in his study entitled "A Study on the Factors Influencing Study Habits of Tenth Class Students in Their Academic Achievements." The study focused on gender, locality, and school management type on tenth class students' academic achievement. It is showed in the study that these factors influence the study habits of the respondents. The research emphasizes the importance of developing good study habits such as time management.

According to the study of Castillo et al. (2023) entitled The Impact of Study Habits on The Academic Performance of Senior High School Students Amidst Blended Learning, a good study habit can play a significant role in helping to contribute to a great academic performance. Furthermore, Mudasir (2019) highlighted that students' academic achievement is greatly influenced by their study habits. Academic Success and Study Habits are tied to and dependent upon one another. Study habits are a well-organized and purposeful routine of study that has been obtained by students in their commitment to comprehending academic material and passing exams.

A study by Nair (2020) entitled Study Habits and Its Impact on Academic Performance in English of Secondary School Students in Kalaburgi Region also shared that there is significant relationship between study habits and students' academic performance. It was revealed that the better the students study habits, the higher their learning achievement. Moreover, in support of the study aforementioned, Ebele & Olofu (2019), in their study entitled "Study Habit and Its Impact on Secondary School Students' Academic Performance in Biology in the Federal Capital Territory," revealed that there is a significant relationship between the said variables. In addition, a study by Kwakye (2020) entitled Study Habits and Academic Performance of Junior High School Pupils in Akuapem South District of Ghana: Implications for Educational Practice, stated that good study habits are essential ingredients for better academic performance.

Delay Avoidance

According to the study of Khanam, Sahu, Rao, Kar & Quazi (2017), Time management is one of the skills that impact the students' academic performance. The researchers have conducted a study about time management or delay avoidance and the respondents' academic achievement, which are the medical students in Odisha. The study revealed that the respondents who obtained a high percentage also had a high mean score on general time management. And so, it means that time management is critical to improving one's academic performance.

Moreover, a study conducted in Mandaue City, Cebu by Capuno (2019) entitled Attitudes, Study Habits, and Academic Performance of Junior High School Students in Mathematics revealed that there is a positive correlation between delay avoidance and academic performance of the respondents. It was determined that time management and study habits of students are important elements influencing their academic achievement.

However, in "Metacognition, study habits and attitudes," the study revealed no significant relationship between delay avoidance and study habits and attitudes for low and medium achievers. Still, a significant relationship was found in students who have high achievement.

Work Methods

On the study of J.P. Fouche (2019), good study habits like doing assignments, participation in class, managing time, always being focused, and working hard or in short, having good work methods showed a positive correlation with academic performance. Generally, it shows that appropriate study habits such as work methods may help students improve their academic performance in school to be more efficient. It also shows that bad study habits have a significant negative relationship with the students' academic performance, the opposite of the factors mentioned above of good study habits.

In the study of Rabia et al. (2017), results showed that there is a significant relationship between study habits and academic performance of the students especially in terms of work methods, which was checked by using chi-square on the sample of 270 students taken from two colleges of Pakistan. In the study of Alimohamadi et al. (2018), entitled "Relation study between study habit and academic performance of nursing students in Hamadan," they attempted to examine the relationship of the study habits of the students and its relationship with the academic performance in a sample of 220 nursing students at Hamadan University of Medical Sciences. Results also showed a positive correlation between the mean score of study habits in terms of work methods and academic performance of the students.

However, In the study of Lawrence (2014) entitled "Relationship between Study Habits and Academic Achievement of Higher Secondary School Students," the present study was conducted to find the significant relationship between the study variables. The findings showed no significant difference between the study habits and the academic achievement of higher secondary schools.

The study of Daño (2017) entitled "Learning Styles, Study Habits, and Academic Performance of Nursing Students," investigated the academic performance and learning styles. Study habits of the first, second, and third-year nursing students at Cebu Normal University during the school year 2001-2002, to know whether a relationship existed among the variables. The locale of the study was the College of Nursing at Cebu

Normal University. The study respondents consisted of 159 nursing students, 58 students from the first year, 66 from the second year, and 35 from the third year.

Furthermore, the study utilized the descriptive survey method to use the inventory and documentary records as the main instrument in gathering data. Documentary records, specifically the teachers' grade sheets, were used to evaluate the students' academic performance. It was revealed that the study and learning styles of the first year, second year, and third year nursing students at Cebu Normal University during the school year 2001-2002 affected their academic performance. The better the study habits and the more balanced the learning styles, the better the academic performance. Therefore, it was recommended that there is a need to prepare an instructional unit to help students improve their study habits and balance their learning style.

The research that was mentioned and cited above have shown the relationship between study habits with the students' academic performance. It shows the students' different actions since the studies have different hypotheses that make them different from each other. In general, the related literature and studies gathered and presented in this chapter show the different gaps between the study habits and academic performance.

Research Methods

This study is quantitative in nature and utilized a descriptive-correlational research design. This design was primarily interested in describing relationships among variables, without seeking to establish a causal connection. The researchers adapted a survey questionnaire and finalized it before being distributed to the targeted group of respondents. Descriptive research design aimed to systematically obtain information to describe a phenomenon situation or population. A correlational design investigates variables without the researcher controlling or manipulating any of them.

Results and Discussion

Based on the gathered data, the Grade 12 students' study habits in terms of delay avoidance have an average mean of 2.94 and the Grade 12 students' study habits in terms of work methods has an average mean of 2.82 and both are interpreted as Satisfactory. Moreover, it revealed the level of Grade 12 students' academic performance and showed that the most significant number of respondents, comprising 46.55 % or 27 of the 58 respondents, belonged to the group who recorded very satisfactory grades. There were 21 respondents or 36,21% with outstanding grades, and 15.52% or 9 respondents with a satisfactory grade. Lastly, only 1 (1.72%) respondent have a satisfactory grade.

The researchers correlated the respondents' study habits in terms of delay avoidance and work methods with the respondents' academic performance amid the modular learning set-up in the first semester. They found out that there is no significant relationship between the respondents' study habits in terms of delay avoidance and their academic performance with a computed r value of 0.0891. However, it also revealed that there is a significant relationship between the respondents' study habits in terms of work methods and their academic performance with a computer r value of 0.4035.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers concluded that the Grade 12 students' study habits in terms of delay avoidance revealed non-significance on their academic performance but there is a significant correlation between Work Methods and Academic Performance. Thus, students get high grades when they develop study techniques even more than managing time and promptness in accomplishing tasks. This would imply that students who used effective study procedures have a high chance in getting a better academic performance.

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